

Risk Factors Determinants of Subtotal Cholecystectomy: Experience at a Second-Level Hospital in Mexico.

Rosario Martínez-Victoria¹, Jesús M. Castro-Vargas¹, Violeta Ibarra-Silverio², María De Los Ángeles Martínez-Ferretiz³

¹4th-Year Resident in General Surgery, Department of General Surgery, Hospital General de Cancún “Dr. Jesús Kumate Rodríguez”, Servicios de Salud del Instituto Mexicano del Seguro Social para el Bienestar (IMSS-BIENESTAR). Programa de posgrado de la Facultad de Medicina, Universidad Autónoma de Yucatán, MEX

²3rd-Year Resident in General Surgery, Department of General Surgery, Hospital General de Cancún “Dr. Jesús Kumate Rodríguez”, Servicios de Salud del Instituto Mexicano del Seguro Social para el Bienestar (IMSS-BIENESTAR). Programa de posgrado de la Facultad de Medicina, Universidad Autónoma de Yucatán, MEX

³General surgeon, Hospital General de Cancún, Servicios de Salud del Instituto Mexicano del Seguro Social para el Bienestar (IMSSBIENESTAR), MEX.

ABSTRACT

Objective: To identify the clinical and surgical factors associated with performing subtotal cholecystectomy in patients undergoing surgery for cholecystitis at the General Hospital of Cancún, in order to anticipate cases of greater surgical complexity, improve preoperative planning, and reduce the risk of complications.

Methods: A search was conducted of the records of patients who underwent total or subtotal cholecystectomy from January 2023 to December 2024. Chi-square and Student's t-tests were applied to compare between both groups. This was complemented with multivariate regression to adjust for possible confounding factors.

Results: A total of 385 patients were analyzed, of whom 345 (89.6%) underwent total cholecystectomy and 40 (10.4%) underwent subtotal cholecystectomy. Patients with subtotal cholecystectomy were older (44.8 ± 16.8 vs. 38.8 ± 14.1 years, $p = 0.033$) and heavier (76.46 ± 17.14 vs. 70.19 ± 15.02 kg, $p = 0.034$). They were also associated with greater gallbladder wall thickness (5.9 ± 2.5 vs. 4.0 ± 2.3 mm, $p < 0.001$) and a higher white blood cell count (13.1 ± 5.10 vs. 10.5 ± 6.23 cells/ml, $p = 0.005$).

Conclusions: Subtotal cholecystectomy was significantly associated with factors suggesting greater complexity of the condition, such as older age, greater weight, presence of diabetes, and wall thickening. Identifying these preoperative factors could help anticipate the need for a subtotal technique and optimize surgical preparation.

KEYWORDS: subtotal cholecystectomy, risk factors, acute cholecystitis, symptomatic cholelithiasis

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
30 November 2025

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

INTRODUCTION

Cholecystectomy is one of the most frequent surgical procedures in general surgery. It is estimated that between 10 and 15% of the western population will develop gallstones during their lifetime, this being the main indication for cholecystectomy.¹ Since its creation, this procedure has undergone several modifications, the best known of which is

the change from an open to a laparoscopic approach, which currently constitutes the therapeutic standard, supported by international and national guidelines.²

However, there are some other clinical scenarios in which the anatomy of the hepatocystic triangle may be distorted, making it difficult to obtain a critical safety view and significantly increasing the risk of bile duct injury.³ For these

Risk Factors Determinants of Subtotal Cholecystectomy: Experience at a Second-Level Hospital in Mexico.

cases, Bornman and Terblanche developed an alternative procedure in 1985, which consists of partial resection of the gallbladder, preserving a remnant of the wall or cystic stump, with the aim of protecting the common bile duct.⁴ This procedure is known as subtotal cholecystectomy, of which there are two classic variants: the fenestrated technique, which leaves the gallbladder cavity open allowing drainage, and the reconstituted technique, which sutures the remnant to form a "neo-gallbladder body".⁵

Previous studies have shown that subtotal cholecystectomy reduces the need for conversion to open surgery and decreases the rate of major bile duct injury, although with a transient increase in the risk of bile leak and residual cholelithiasis.^{6,7} Recent meta-analyses suggest that it offers better results in terms of severe morbidity compared to open conversion, without compromising hospital stay or quality of life in less complex settings.^{8,9} This utility has led to international guidelines such as those from Tokyo 2018¹⁰, as well as the Consensus of the American Society of Gastrointestinal Surgeons and Endoscopists¹¹ It is recommended in cases where it is not safe to completely remove the gallbladder due to the risk of injury.

Although some recommendations indicate that its use should be considered when safe dissection is not possible, its adoption varies widely, accounting for less than 10% of cholecystectomies performed,^{12,13} depending on the surgeon's experience, the availability of hospital resources, and certain patient-specific factors.

Several factors have been proposed as predictors of the need for subtotal cholecystectomy, including advanced age, obesity, ultrasound findings such as parietal thickening > 4 mm or pericholecystic fluid, a diagnosis of gangrenous cholecystitis, a grade III classification according to the 2018 Tokyo guidelines, a history of upper abdominal surgery, and Mirizzi syndrome.¹³⁻¹⁵ However, the results are heterogeneous, and these studies did not include the Mexican population. Importantly, to our knowledge, there are no specific studies in the Mexican population that seek to evaluate the prevalence of subtotal cholecystectomy and factors associated with its use.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A retrospective study of the medical records of patients who underwent cholecystectomy in our General Surgery service was conducted. Consecutive records of patients who underwent surgery between January 1, 2023, and December 31, 2024, were reviewed. All patients over 18 years of age who underwent open or laparoscopic cholecystectomy as the primary procedure or in conjunction with other abdominal procedures were included. Patients for whom the extent of resection (total or subtotal) was not specified were excluded. Subtotal cholecystectomy was defined as the resection of the gallbladder body and fundus leaving a cystic duct stump or posterior wall, with or without closure of the cystic duct,

while total cholecystectomy involved complete excision of the gallbladder with proximal clipping of the cystic duct.

A significance level of 95% was considered for statistical analysis. Normality was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test. Since there were no outliers in our sample, continuous variables were expressed as mean and standard deviation, while categorical variables were expressed as frequency and proportion. A comparison between groups was performed using Student's t-test for numerical variables and Pearson's chi-squared test for categorical variables. Finally, variables with statistically significant differences and those with clinical relevance were included in the multivariate analysis through logistic regression. The analyses were performed using IBM® SPSS® Statistics v27

The protocol was approved by the hospital's Local Ethics and Research Committee (CEI-2025-020-HGC and CI-2025-020-HGC opinions). As this was a retrospective study, informed consent was waived; confidentiality was ensured through alphanumeric coding of records and compliance with NOM-004-SSA3-2012. The research was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

RESULTS

A total of 385 patients were enrolled, of whom 89.6% (n = 345) underwent total cholecystectomy and 10.4% (n = 40) underwent subtotal cholecystectomy. Females predominated in both groups; however, a higher proportion of men was observed in the subtotal cholecystectomy group compared to the total cholecystectomy group (43.6% vs. 17.4%; $p < 0.001$). Age was significantly higher in the subtotal cholecystectomy group (44.8 ± 16.8 years vs. 38.8 ± 14.1 years; $p = 0.033$), as was weight (76.46 ± 17.14 kg vs. 70.19 ± 15.02 kg; $p = 0.034$), with no difference in body mass index (BMI). The proportion of patients with a history of previous abdominal surgery was higher in the total cholecystectomy group (52.8% vs. 35.0%; $p = 0.094$), although this difference did not reach statistical significance. Finally, the presence of type 2 diabetes was significantly more frequent in the subtotal cholecystectomy group (22.5% vs. 9.9%; $p = 0.032$; Table 1). As expected, the open surgical approach was significantly more common in the total cholecystectomy group (75.9%) than in the subtotal cholecystectomy group (25.0%; $p < 0.001$). Elective surgery was performed at a significantly higher rate in the total cholecystectomy group (55.2%) compared to the subtotal group (13.2%; $p < 0.001$). There was a trend in patients undergoing subtotal surgery to have a symptom duration greater than 72 hours (80.0% vs. 61.8%), although this difference did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.064$; Table 2).

Regarding laboratory and imaging studies, it was observed that patients undergoing subtotal cholecystectomy presented with greater gallbladder wall thickness (5.9 ± 2.5 mm vs. 4.0 ± 2.3 mm; $p < 0.001$; Figure 1), as well as significantly higher levels of leukocytes (13.1 ± 5.10 vs. 10.5 ± 6.23 cells/ml; $p =$

Risk Factors Determinants of Subtotal Cholecystectomy: Experience at a Second-Level Hospital in Mexico.

0.005) and neutrophils (10.15 ± 4.88 vs. 7.42 ± 5.01 cells/ml; $p = 0.001$; Figure 2).

Finally, in the multivariate analysis, only age and elective cholecystectomy (compared to emergency surgery) retained their statistical significance, indicating that the other variables have a codependent effect on each other (Table 3).

DISCUSSION

In our series of 385 cholecystectomies, the prevalence of subtotal cholecystectomy was 10.4%, a figure slightly higher than that described by recent reviews and international cohort studies.^{15,16} This finding could be due to multiple factors. First, it has been reported that patients with acute cholecystitis in Mexico and other Latin American countries experience delays in diagnosis and treatment, leading to a higher prevalence of complications, which can be as high as 20%.^{17,18} In addition, our hospital has a high volume of patients, allowing surgeons to become more familiar with this technique and therefore adopt it more frequently compared to other centers. Furthermore, it is important to note that previous studies have shown that increased experience with this technique reduces the need for conversion to open surgery and complications.¹⁹

Multivariate analysis identified two independent predictors of subtotal cholecystectomy: male sex (OR 2.182; 95% CI 1.01–4.73; $p = 0.048$) and the presence of emergency surgery (OR 4.609; 95% CI 1.62–13.13; $p = 0.004$). Both factors are consistent with previous publications, notably a study of more than 2,700 patients by Lucoq et al.¹⁶ in which a Random Forest model (a machine learning classification technique based on random sets of decision trees) was trained and validated²⁰, reported that the factors most associated with predicting the need for subtotal cholecystectomy were age > 60 years, male sex, diabetes mellitus, acute cholecystitis, greater severity of cholecystitis (CRP > 90 mg/L), ≥ 3 admissions for biliary causes, preoperative ERCP with or without stent placement, preoperative cholecystostomy, and emergency cholecystectomy (AUC = 0.84).

Following this study, another by Tang et al. with 916 patients demonstrated that the probability of performing a subtotal cholecystectomy was not influenced by the surgeon's experience (≤ 5 vs. > 5 years; $p = 0.09$). However, a higher adjusted probability of subtotal cholecystectomy was found to be associated with older age (OR 1.23, $P = 0.03$), male sex (OR 2.59, $P < 0.01$), white blood cell count > 10.3 (OR 2.02, $P = 0.02$), and a preoperative diagnosis of acute-on-chronic cholecystitis (OR 5.47, $P < 0.01$).²¹

Although outcomes such as mortality or ICU stay were not assessed, it is important to note that patients undergoing this procedure, compared to those converted to open cholecystectomy, typically have a shorter hospital stay, less need for intensive care admission, and a shorter operative time, demonstrating that it is a safe and potentially superior technique in critically ill patients.²²

Other factors identified in the univariate analysis (such as age, weight, presence of diabetes mellitus, gallbladder wall thickening, emergency surgery, and elevated leukocyte and neutrophil counts) have been previously described as predictors of complicated or more severe cholecystitis. This condition could influence the surgeon's decision to opt for a subtotal rather than a total approach.^{23–26}

Our study is not without limitations. The retrospective, single-center design introduces selection bias. Furthermore, the decision to perform a subtotal cholecystectomy depended on the surgeon's judgment and not on a standardized protocol. Certain predictors described as factors associated with subtotal cholecystectomy (e.g., TG-18 grade, CT findings, and CRP values) were not analyzed in our cohort. Finally, the small number of subtotal cholecystectomies results in wide confidence intervals for some variables and limits statistical power. However, to our knowledge, this is the first Mexican study to explore multivariable predictors of subtotal cholecystectomy and confirms the applicability of factors described in other countries. Our findings support the idea that male patients admitted for emergency cholecystectomy are more likely to require a subtotal approach, probably due to a more severe clinical profile. However, future multicenter studies should validate these findings, including other inflammatory biomarkers and comparing postoperative outcomes between both approaches.

CONCLUSIONS

In this cohort of patients undergoing cholecystectomy, older age and the procedure being performed in a surgical emergency setting were independently associated with the choice of a subtotal approach. In the bivariate analysis, older age, greater weight, the presence of diabetes, a longer duration of symptoms, greater gallbladder wall thickness, and increased inflammatory markers (leukocytes and neutrophils) were also associated with this approach.

In clinical practice, early identification of these factors is recommended to help anticipate a complex gallbladder approach and, thereby, optimize surgical planning and decision-making. However, multicenter, prospective studies with larger sample sizes are needed to confirm these predictors and promote their integration into institutional protocols and clinical practice guidelines.

REFERENCES

- I. Wang X, Yu W, Jiang G, et al. Global Epidemiology of Gallstones in the 21st Century: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Clin Gastroenterol Hepatol.* 2024;22(8):1586-1595. doi:10.1016/j.cgh.2024.01.051
- II. Pisano M, Allievi N, Gurusamy K, et al. 2020 World Society of Emergency Surgery updated guidelines for the diagnosis and treatment of acute calculus cholecystitis. *World J Emerg Surg* 2020;15(1):61. doi:10.1186/s13017-020-00336-x

Risk Factors Determinants of Subtotal Cholecystectomy: Experience at a Second-Level Hospital in Mexico.

- III. Santos BF, Brunt LM, Pucci MJ. The Difficult Gallbladder: A Safe Approach to a Dangerous Problem. *J Laparoendosc Adv Surg Tech A*2017;27(6):571-578. doi:10.1089/lap.2017.0038
- IV. Bornman PC, Terblanche J. Subtotal cholecystectomy: for the difficult gallbladder in portal hypertension and cholecystitis. *Surgery*1985;98(1):1-6.
- V. Strasberg SM, Pucci MJ, Brunt LM, Deziel DJ. Subtotal Cholecystectomy—"Fenestrating" vs "Reconstituting" Subtypes and the Prevention of Bile Duct Injury: Definition of the Optimal Procedure in Difficult Operative Conditions. *J Am Coll Surg*2016;222(1):89-96. doi:10.1016/j.jamcollsurg.2015.09.019
- VI. Deng SX, Sharma BT, Ebeye T, et al. Laparoscopic subtotal cholecystectomy for the difficult gallbladder: Evolution of technique at a single teaching hospital. *Surgery*2024;175(4):955-962. doi:10.1016/j.surg.2023.12.026
- VII. Ibrahim R, Abdalkodous M, Mahendran B, Mownah OA, Nawara H, Aroori S. Subtotal cholecystectomy: is it a safe option for difficult gall bladders? *Ann R Coll Surg Engl*2023;105(5):455-460. doi:10.1308/rcsann.2021.0291
- VIII. Ravendran K, Elmoraly A, Thomas CS, et al. Fenestrating Versus Reconstituting Subtotal Cholecystectomy: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis on Bile Leak, Bile Duct Injury, and Outcomes. *Cureus*16(10):e72769. doi:10.7759/cureus.72769
- IX. Ramírez-Giraldo C, Torres-Cuellar A, Van-Londoño I. State of the art in subtotal cholecystectomy: An overview. *Front Surg*2023;10:1142579. doi:10.3389/fsurg.2023.1142579
- X. Okamoto K, Suzuki K, Takada T, et al. Tokyo Guidelines 2018: flowchart for the management of acute cholecystitis. *J Hepatobiliary Pancreat Sci*2018;25(1):55-72. doi:10.1002/jhbp.516
- XI. Brunt LM, Deziel DJ, Telem DA, et al. Safe Cholecystectomy Multi-society Practice Guideline and State of the Art Consensus Conference on Prevention of Bile Duct Injury During Cholecystectomy. *Ann Surg*2020;272(1):3-23. doi:10.1097/SLA.0000000000003791
- XII. Booyse K, Lindemann J, Calitz M, Bernon M, Jonas E, Kloppers C. Laparoscopic subtotal cholecystectomy outcomes across a low- and middle-income country metropolitan health service. *World J Surg*2024;48(6):1323-1330. doi:10.1002/wjs.12180
- XIII. Nzenwa IC, Mesri M, Lunevicius R. Risks associated with subtotal cholecystectomy and the factors influencing them: A systematic review and meta-analysis of 85 studies published between 1985 and 2020. *Surgery*2021;170(4):1014-1023. doi:10.1016/j.surg.2021.03.036
- XIV. Chowbey PK, Sharma A, Khullar R, Mann V, Baijal M, Vashistha A. Laparoscopic subtotal cholecystectomy: a review of 56 procedures. *J Laparoendosc Adv Surg Tech A*2000;10(1):31-34. doi:10.1089/lap.2000.10.31
- XV. Elshaer M, Gravante G, Thomas K, Sorge R, Al-Hamali S, Ebdewi H. Subtotal cholecystectomy for "difficult gallbladders": systematic review and meta-analysis. *JAMA Surg*2015;150(2):159-168. doi:10.1001/jamasurg.2014.1219
- XVI. Lucocq J, Hamilton D, Bakhiet A, et al. Derivation and validation of a predictive model for subtotal cholecystectomy. *Surg Endosc*2024;38(11):6551-6559. doi:10.1007/s00464-024-11241-8
- XVII. Muñoz-Muñoz M, Macías-Rodríguez MG, Castañeda-Rocha SI, et al. Prevalence of complicated cholecystitis during the COVID-19 pandemic in a secondary care hospital. *General Surgeon*2023;45(3):132-137. doi:10.35366/112922
- XVIII. Castro F, Galindo J, Bejarano M. Complications of acute cholecystitis in patients undergoing emergency surgery. *Colombian Journal of Surgery*2008;23(1):16-21.
- XIX. LeCompte MT, Robbins KJ, Williams GA, et al. Less is more in the difficult gallbladder: recent evolution of subtotal cholecystectomy in a single HPB unit. *Surg Endosc.* 2021;35(7):3249-3257. doi:10.1007/s00464-020-07759-2
- XX. Rigatti SJ. Random Forest. *J Insur Med*2017;47(1):31-39. doi:10.17849/inism-47-01-31-39.1
- XXI. Tang A, Cohan CM, Beattie G, Mooney CM, Chiang A, Keeley JA. Factors that Predict the Need for Subtotal Cholecystectomy. *Am Surg*2021;87(8):1245-1251. doi:10.1177/0003134820979783
- XXII. Grossman H, Holder KG, Freedle C, Dhanasekara CS, Dissanaikie S. Comparing Outcomes of Subtotal Cholecystectomy Versus Open Cholecystectomy as Bailout Procedures for the Difficult Gallbladder. *Am Surg*2023;89(12):5372-5378. doi:10.1177/00031348221148345
- XXIII. Mahmood F, Akingboye A, Malam Y, Thakkar M, Jambulingam P. Complicated Acute Cholecystitis: The Role of C-Reactive Protein and Neutrophil-Lymphocyte Ratio as Predictive Markers of Severity. *Cureus*2021;13(2):e13592. doi:10.7759/cureus.13592
- XXIV. Charalel RA, Jeffrey RB, Shin LK. Complicated cholecystitis: the complementary roles of sonography and computed tomography. *Ultrasound Q*2011;27(3):161-170. doi:10.1097/RUQ.0b013e31822a33e8

Risk Factors Determinants of Subtotal Cholecystectomy: Experience at a Second-Level Hospital in Mexico.

XXV. Gojayev A, Karakaya E, Erkent M, et al. A novel approach to distinguish complicated and non-complicated acute cholecystitis: Decision tree method. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2023;102(19):e33749. doi:10.1097/MD.00000000000033749

XXVI. Stoica PL, Serban D, Bratu DG, et al. Predictive Factors for Difficult Laparoscopic Cholecystectomies in Acute Cholecystitis. *Diagnostics (Basel)* 2024;14(3):346. doi:10.3390/diagnostics14030346

Tables

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of the population. BMI: Body mass index.

Variable	Total cholecystectomy (n = 345)	Subtotal cholecystectomy (n = 40)	p-value
Sex, male – n, %	60 (17.4%)	17 (43.6%)	<0.001
Age (years)	38.8 ± 14.1	44.8 ± 16.8	0.033
Weight (kg)	70.19 ± 15.02	76.46 ± 17.14	0.034
Height (m)	1.55 ± 0.08	1.58 ± 0.10	0.095
BMI (kg/m ²)	28.8 ± 5.8	30.6 ± 6.4	0.109
Previous abdominal surgery – n, %	182 (52.8%)	14 (35.0%)	0.094
Type 2 Diabetes – n, %	34 (9.9%)	9 (22.5%)	0.032

Table 2. Surgical and paraclinical characteristics.

Variable	Total cholecystectomy (n = 345)	Subtotal cholecystectomy (n = 40)	p-value
Open approach – n, %	262 (75.9%)	10 (25.0%)	<0.001
Symptoms > 72hr – n (%)	97 (61.8%)	28 (80.0%)	0.064
Elective surgery – n (%)	191 (55.2%)	5 (13.2%)	<0.001
Wall thickness (mm)	4.0 ± 2.3	5.9 ± 2.5	<0.001
Leukocytes (cells/ml)	10.5 ± 6.23	13.1 ± 5.10	0.005
Neutrophils (cells/ml)	7.42 (5.01)	10.15 (4.88)	0.001

Table 3. Results of the multivariate logistic regression. CI: confidence interval, OR: odds ratio.

Variable	OR	CI	p-value
Sex (Male)	2.182	1.01 – 4.73	0.048
Diabetes	2.064	0.724 – 5.88	0.175
Age	1.018	0.99 – 1.046	0.213
Weight	1.006	0.98 – 1.02	0.617
Leukocytes	1.017	0.833 – 1.24	0.868
Neutrophils	0.997	0.789 – 1.25	0.980
Wall thickness	1.14	0.98 – 1.37	0.074
Emergency Surgery	4.609	1.62 – 13.13	0.004

Figure Captions

Figure 1. Comparison of wall thickness in millimeters between patients undergoing subtotal and total cholecystectomy.

Figure 2. Comparison of neutrophil and leukocyte levels between patients undergoing subtotal and total cholecystectomy.